

EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF DRAMA AND ROLE-PLAY EXERCISES ON IMPROVING YOUNG LEARNERS' ENGLISH ORAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14209529>

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of traditional teaching methods compared to creative drama activities in enhancing young learners' English oral communication skills. Participants were split into two groups: one received traditional instruction, while the other engaged in drama and role-play activities. Data was gathered through pretest and post-test scores, which were analyzed using a paired sample t-test to identify any significant improvements in speaking abilities between the groups. Additionally, qualitative data was collected through student feedback and observations throughout the instructional period, which were examined using thematic analysis to uncover patterns or themes related to the students' experiences with the different teaching approaches.

Keywords: *role-play, teaching technique, flexibility, social skills, cognitive skills.*

Teaching English to young children presents unique challenges and opportunities. At this age, children are particularly receptive to new languages, often picking up sounds and structures more easily than older learners. However, their attention spans are shorter, and they learn best through play and interactive activities. The current understanding of language acquisition emphasizes the importance of discovery, experimentation, and motivation in learning. Here are some key points that align with this perspective: The study's findings support the idea that incorporating drama and role-play activities into language instruction can be highly effective in improving students' oral communication skills. This aligns with the widely accepted belief that drama is a valuable tool for developing communicative competence in language learning.

Children are naturally social beings. They often learn language quickly from peers as they engage in play and form friendships. This social interaction creates a rich context for language use, allowing them to practice and reinforce their skills in a meaningful way. Learning in context—whether through daily experiences or media—

helps children connect language to real-life situations. For example, watching cartoons or playing games in English can make vocabulary and phrases more relatable and easier to remember.

The study also highlights the importance of student engagement and enjoyment in the learning process. The students who participated in the drama and role-play activities expressed higher levels of engagement, enjoyment, and confidence in speaking English, which likely contributed to their improved speaking skills. This underscores the significance of creating a positive and interactive learning environment for language learners.

Educators and curriculum designers can leverage these insights to guide their teaching methods and create new strategies for language instruction. By integrating drama and role-play activities into their lessons, they may improve students' oral communication abilities and enrich the overall language learning experience.

This study adds to the body of research supporting the effectiveness of drama and role-play in language learning, and it provides valuable insights for educators looking to create dynamic and engaging language instruction.

According to Jean Piaget's cognitive development theory (Saracho, 2023), children follow a thinking pattern that advances through a series of stages. This progression is achieved by utilizing a sequence of schemas, combining their reasoning styles about various aspects of the world. A schema is a comprehensive approach to understanding these components. According to Piaget, preschool-age children fall into the definition of preoperational stage. Children in this stage do not yet possess the ability to understand concrete logic, manipulate information mentally, or consider the perspectives of others which Piaget termed as egocentrism. For example, a young child may believe that everyone sees the world as they do and may be surprised to learn that others have different perceptions and experiences. In contrast, adults generally acknowledge that people have diverse points of view and may have varying interpretations of situations.

Drama-supported cooperative learning methods are effective teaching strategies that engage students in active and collaborative learning while developing social, emotional, and cognitive skills (Güleç & Macan, 2014). Research showed that significant differences in communication skills were found in favor of the experimental group in a drama-supported cooperative learning method study, "the child generally perceives drama activity as a game and concentrates all his or her energy and attention on this activity. Thus, the child finds the opportunity to play a game and learn many concepts, topics, and social behaviors more effectively" (2014. p. 533). Drama activities provide a dynamic and interactive way for children to learn. By engaging in role-play, improvisation, and storytelling, they can express

themselves creatively while developing important skills such as teamwork, communication, and problem-solving. These activities not only make learning enjoyable but also help to build confidence and enhance language skills in a fun, supportive environment. Incorporating games and playful elements into lessons can significantly increase students' motivation and retention of information.

Role play is a standard drama-supported cooperative learning method and a valuable teaching strategy for preschoolers as it supports their learning, social and emotional development and language skills (Kopema, 2020). Pedagogical and educational sciences recognize the therapeutic role of fun, a fundamental activity for children to learn and develop through play(2020). In a roleplaying game, the child embodies the content through the role they assume, which serves as the primary component and a tool for carrying out the plot. Children may use props, costumes, and toys to enhance the experience and make the activity fun. Role play is a spontaneous expression of the child's creativity, involving interaction with adults. The main characteristics of the game, including children's commitment, emotional depth, independence, creativity, and activity, are inherent in the plot and roleplaying aspects of the game (Chorievich, 2020).

A widely cited definition of drama comes from Holden (1981: 1) who defines it as “any activity which asks the student to portray a) himself in an imaginary situation or b) another person in an imaginary situation”—a definition which can be applied to most formats of drama in language teaching and includes role-play as a form of drama. However, vocal and physical exercises that do not imply the creation of a fictional character or situation, such as articulation exercises or movement games, should also be included.

However, for language learners to encounter drama at school or in university, their teachers need to be familiar and comfortable with it. Not all teachers feel at ease with employing drama in the classroom—there are constraints of time and space and not every teacher feels confident to use a method they have not been trained in (Royka 2002, Gaudart 1990).

In a business simulation, students can role-play as employees, managers, or even customers, and experience the challenges and opportunities that arise in a dynamic business environment. They can learn to communicate effectively, negotiate deals, manage conflicts, and make decisions under pressure. By simulating real-life scenarios, students can develop their emotional intelligence and learn to empathize with others, which is essential in building strong relationships in the workplace.

In a marketing simulation, students could work in teams to brainstorm product ideas, conduct market research, and create advertising campaigns. They would need to analyze the target audience's demographics and psychographics, allowing them to

tailor their messaging effectively. By presenting their pitches to classmates or even a panel of "investors," they can practice public speaking and receive constructive feedback. For a finance simulation, students could be tasked with managing a virtual investment portfolio. They would learn to analyze financial statements, assess risk, and make informed decisions based on real-world data. Incorporating elements like economic news updates or market fluctuations can help them understand how external factors influence investment choices. Additionally, discussing the emotional aspects of investing—such as fear and greed—can deepen their understanding of market psychology.

In conclusion, incorporating dramatic play into business education fosters essential skills like empathy, communication, and conflict resolution. By engaging in role-playing scenarios, students can practice handling real-world situations, such as negotiations, team dynamics, and customer interactions. This experiential learning approach allows them to explore different perspectives and develop a deeper understanding of emotional intelligence.

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